

Leveraging Artificial Intelligence Technologies For Successful Business Management By Entrepreneurs In Anambra State

Anuka Chijioke Bernadine¹ & Amaugo, Ernest Nkwachi²

^{1,2}Department of Business Education

School of Vocational and Technical Education

Nwafor Orizu College of Education, Nsugbe, Nigeria

¹Uniquebernadine3210@gmail.com/ 08062323605

²amaugoernest170@gmail.com/ 07032894732

ABSTRACT

This study determined the extent AI technologies are leveraged for successful business management by entrepreneurs in Anambra State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted survey research design, and the population consisted of 1,813 registered SMEs managers in Anambra State. The sample of 317 managers of SMEs was drawn through Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table of determination. A-16 item structured questionnaire titled “Extent of Leveraging AI by Entrepreneurs for Successful Business Management (ELIAESBM) was used for data collection. Face and content validity of the instrument was determined using opinions of three experts in the field of education. The reliability of instrument was ascertained using pilot-testing method and data collected analyzed with Cronbach alpha formula which yielded correlation coefficients of .88 and .79 for clusters B1 to B2 with an overall reliability coefficient of .84 obtained. Mean, standard deviation and t-test were used for data analysis. Findings revealed that entrepreneurs to a very small extent leverage both machine learning technologies and natural language processing (NLP) technologies for successful business management in Anambra State. Years of working experience did not influence their mean ratings in this regard. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that entrepreneurs in Anambra State are not adequately leveraging the impact of AI technologies for enhancing the success of their business management. It was recommended that entrepreneurs in Anambra State should go for more digital skill acquisition trainings to enhance their AI skills. This will help them to leverage AI technologies for successful business management.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Technologies Successful Business Management, Entrepreneurs

INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian nation cannot exist without progress and economic growth. The idea that the country's economy is vital to the survival and successful functioning of every aspect of society, including individuals, is not hyperbole. Because of this, the Nigerian government invests in the economy and invites private citizens to support the strong economic growth of the nation. The growth of entrepreneurs in the country was aided by this encouragement. An entrepreneur is a person who launches new goods, promotes innovation, and gathers resources in order to expand a company with little funding. Regardless of gender, entrepreneurs either run their own companies or employ others to do so. In this study, an entrepreneur will also be referred to as a small and medium business (SMB) manages if they own their

company, run it themselves, or hire someone to run it for them. Entrepreneurs are able to manage and maintain their businesses because of their entrepreneurial skills. In agreement, Adeyemi and Olufemi (2016) stated that entrepreneurs are essential to Nigeria's economic and social development because they foster innovation, create jobs, alleviate poverty, and ensure economic diversification. Their entrepreneurial abilities allow them to effectively manage technological, financial, and human resources in order to achieve business objectives, which is what successful business management is all about.

Effective business management entails overseeing a variety of business operations to make sure they function properly (Kaufmannm 2023). Successful business management, according to Gitman (2018), is the efficient management of an organization's assets, activities, and plans in order to accomplish its objectives and guarantee long-term viability. Planning, organizing, staffing, leading, and controlling all while keeping the company's mission, vision, and goals front and center are essential components of effective business management. Hiring, developing, and retaining qualified staff members are also essential components of effective business management. In addition to managing performance and inspiring teams, managers must cultivate a positive workplace culture. Armstrong and Taylor noted that businesses need to constantly innovate in order to remain competitive. Remaining relevant in the marketplace requires embracing new technologies, adjusting to shifts in the market, and encouraging creativity.

Due to fierce competition from larger businesses, Nigerian small and medium-scale businesses must embrace and innovate with digital technologies. As stated by Seth et al. (2020), digitization enables entrepreneurs to catch up to larger ones. Joel et al. (2023) contended however, that a large number of Nigerian business owners do not fully employ digital tools for managing their businesses. Digital technologies improve products, simplify operations, and adapt to market shifts (Oduntan & Isere, 2022). In addition to increasing productivity, important digital technologies such as automation, e-commerce, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence (AI) also enable businesses to scale and cut expenses, increasing their competitiveness in the global economy.

The ability of computers to mimic human intellectual capacities like reasoning, problem solving, and decision making is known as AI. By evaluating customer behaviour and preferences, spotting talent shortages, and providing training programmes, AI is revolutionizing business management (Gupta & Katoch, 2023). Additionally, it enhances business procedures by making them more customer-focused, data-driven, and efficient. AI can also be a strategic tool, enhancing the abilities of entrepreneurs and helping them create business plans in a complex, dynamic environment. Overall, AI is an important instrument for commercial success. Robotics, machine learning and data analytics, natural language processing, AI-driven innovations, AI-powered decision-making, and AI on business models are examples of AI technologies.

A type of AI tool called machine learning (ML) helps computers learn and make decisions without explicit programming by using statistical techniques. ML is predicated on the idea that computers are capable of learning from data, identifying patterns, and coming to conclusions with minimal help from people. Takyar (2024) stated that ML technologies support data-driven decision-making, job efficiency, cost reduction, efficient planning, quality control, risk management, time savings, and a competitive edge. By automating repetitive tasks, ML technologies reduce human error and expedite processes while analyzing vast volumes of data to give entrepreneurs market analysis. Similarly, Davenport (2018) noted that ML technologies can be used to detect suspicious financial transactions and recommend decisions to manage fraud. Chong et al. (2017) asserted that machine learning (ML) is a powerful AI tool that helps entrepreneurs analyze customer data and behavior to segment markets, target the right audience, and predict future trends and demands. It also helps entrepreneurs make informed decisions about production, marketing, and inventory. Wang et al. (2019) added that ML technologies predict past sales performances, which helps entrepreneurs plan effectively. ML technologies are capable of suggesting products using browsing history and past purchases, improving cross-selling and up-selling strategies. Awoyemi et al. (2017) said that ML technologies can detect unusual transactions, prevent fraud, and make real-time price adjustments based on customer demand, competition, and market conditions. Chatbots can improve customer service by automatically answering frequently asked questions. By predicting demand, reducing

inventory costs, and enhancing delivery schedules, entrepreneurs can use ML technologies to optimize supply chains and logistics.

Business management is being revolutionized by Natural Language Processing (NLP), a branch of AI that uses computers to comprehend and interpret human language, increasing operational efficiency, customer engagement, and decision-making processes (Chaffey, 2020). NLP can help entrepreneurs create targeted advertising strategies, simplify tasks, and analyze unstructured data. NLP is used to search, examine, and extract data from textual input, including figuring out whether an email is trash. Among its benefits are sentiment analysis, improved customer feedback interpretation, Chatbot use for customer support, increased document accuracy, and automatic summary text generation (Ranco, 2021). Entrepreneurs can also benefit from the efficient handling of consumer inquiries by NLP-powered chatbots, which can respond in real time and free up human resources for more difficult jobs. To better understand customer sentiment and enhance their services, they can examine social media comments, reviews, and feedback (Schwartz et al., 2018). By optimizing content for voice searches, entrepreneurs can boost their online visibility with voice-activated technologies.

Many entrepreneurs fail, leaving many questions unanswered despite the nation's population and rapidly expanding market. A loss of roughly 2 million businesses was indicated by the decline in the number of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) from about 41 million in 2017 to 39 million in 2021 (Dan-Awoh, 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic, restricted financial resources, and difficulties associated with globalization were among the reasons given for this decrease. About 30% of Nigeria's 24 million registered MSMEs, or roughly 7.2 million businesses, closed between 2023 and 2024, according to the Nigerian Economic Summit Group (NESG), as stated by Nwite (2025). An estimated N94 trillion was lost as a result of this wave of closures, which was caused by a challenging economic climate, unclear policies, and large multinational divestitures. According to reports, about 80% of Nigerian SMEs fail before they turn five years old. Harsh economic conditions, limited access to capital, multiple taxes, and unethical business practices are all contributing factors.

This issue is also prevalent in Anambra State, as Ufoegbunam and Anekwe (2024) reported that the number of business failures has increased, highlighting the need for entrepreneurs in Rivers State to leverage digital technologies in their operations. Obidile, Nwankwo and Okpara (2022) and Kings (2018) reported that many SMEs in Anambra State die due to challenges such as poor marketing skills, poor financial management, and inadequate leveraging of digital technologies in business operations. Leveraging AI refers to the planned use of AI technologies to maximize overall success of business management. Entrepreneurs with over six years of experience may be more inclined to leverage AI for business management compared to those with less experience. This is likely due to factors such as increased exposure to technological trends, higher risk tolerance, better financial resources, and stronger professional networks. Eromosele (2024) linked many business failures to entrepreneurs' reluctance or failure to adopt digital technologies, including AI. Adeola and Okoye (2021) and Ogunleye and Adebisi (2022) also highlighted that Nigerian entrepreneurs often persist with outdated strategies in areas like marketing, production and customer engagement, contributing to business failures. This study therefore focused on the extent AI technologies are leveraged for successful business management by entrepreneurs in Anambra State.

Statement of the Problem

Entrepreneurs are key drivers of global economic growth, particularly through small and medium scale businesses. They play a critical role in improving living standards, creating jobs, supplying essential goods and services, and boosting GDP. To sustain their growth and survival, entrepreneurs must innovate and leverage emerging technologies such as AI. AI technologies have revolutionized business management worldwide, offering tools that simplify operations, enhance decision-making, and improve customer engagement. However, in Anambra State, Nigeria, it appears that many entrepreneurs are not fully leveraging AI to improve their business outcomes. Despite the potential of AI to boost productivity and competitiveness, many seem to still rely on traditional methods, leading to inefficiencies and stunted business growth. Previous studies have shown that failure to adopt modern technologies, particularly AI, is a key factor in the underperformance of SMEs. There remains a lack of empirical evidence on how

widely AI is leveraged by entrepreneurs in Anambra State for effective business management, which this study sought to address by specifically determining the extent (1) machine learning technologies are leveraged by entrepreneurs for successful business management in Anambra State, (2) Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies are leveraged by entrepreneurs for successful business management in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study;

1. To what extent do entrepreneurs leverage machine learning technologies for successful business management in Anambra State?
2. To what extent do entrepreneurs leverage Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies for successful business management in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of entrepreneurs with 6 and above years of working experience and those below 6 years experience on the extent they leverage Machine Learning technologies for successful business management in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of entrepreneurs on the extent they leverage Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies for successful business management in Anambra State based on years of working experience.

METHODS

This study was adopted survey research design. It was carried out in Anambra State, South-East, Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 1,813 registered SMEs managers in Anambra State. A sample of 317 managers of SMEs was drawn through Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table of determination. Data for the study was collected through structured questionnaire titled “Extent of Leveraging AI by Entrepreneurs for Successful Business Management (ELIAESBM)”. The questionnaire was divided into two sections - A and B. Section A contained item on the demographic information of the respondents such as years of working experience; while section B was in two clusters- B1 and B containing 12 items covering the two research questions. The instrument was structured on a five point rating scale of Very Great Extent (VGE), Great Extent (GE), Moderately Extent (M) – 3, Small Extent (SE) - 2 and Very Small Extent (VSE) – 1. Face and content validity of the instrument was ascertained using three experts, two in entrepreneurship education and one from measurement and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was determined using pilot-testing and data collected were analyzed using Cronbach alpha formula which yielded correlation coefficients of .88 and .79 for clusters B1 to B2 with an overall reliability coefficient of .84 obtained. Data collection instrument was administered to the respondents in their offices with the help of three research assistants, who were briefed on how to administer the instrument. On the spot administration and collection of the questionnaire was used as out of 317 copies of questionnaire distributed, 306(97%) copies were correctly filled and returned, which was used for data analysis. Mean, standard deviation and t-test were used for data analysis. The t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. A null hypothesis was rejected where the P-value is less than the alpha level, but accepted where the P-value is greater than the alpha level. All analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent do entrepreneurs leverage machine learning technologies for successful business management in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Respondents’ Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation on the Extent Entrepreneurs Leverage Machine Learning Technologies for Successful Business Management

S/N	Leveraging of Machine Learning Technologies	X	SD	Remarks
I leverage machine learning technologies to;				
1	to enhance my online customer search	1.63	.81	Small Extent
2	analyze customer data and behavior to segment markets,	1.46	.76	Very Small Extent
3	target the right customer, and predict future demands	1.44	.77	Very Small Extent
4	make better decisions regarding inventory, marketing and production	1.31	.70	Very Small Extent
5	predict past sales performance so as to plan effectively	1.51	.91	Small Extent
6	detect unusual transactions and prevent fraud	1.48	.64	Very Small Extent
Cluster Mean		1.47	.83	Very Small Extent

Table 1 shows the cluster means score of 1.47 and standard deviation score of .83. This is an indication that entrepreneurs in Anambra State leverage machine learning technologies for successful business management to a very small extent. The item by item analysis shows that entrepreneurs to a small extent leverage two items (1 and 5) for successful business management with mean scores of 1.51 to 1.63. The remaining four items are leveraged to a very small extent by entrepreneurs for successful business management with mean scores ranging from 1.31 to 1.48. The standard deviations for all the items ranged from .64 to .91, indicating that the respondents are not wide apart in their ratings.

Research Question 2: *To what extent do entrepreneurs leverage Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies for successful business management in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Respondents’ Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation on the Extent Entrepreneurs Leverage Natural Language Processing (NLP) Technologies for Successful Business Management

S/N	Leveraging of Natural Learning Processing Technologies	X	SD	Remarks
I leverage natural learning processing technologies to;				
7	determine spam e-mail	1.58	.57	Small Extent
8	enhanced accuracy of document being created	1.54	.84	Small Extent
9	improve customer feedback interpretation	1.41	.68	Very Small Extent
10	handle customer inquiries efficiently	1.40	.71	Very Small Extent
11	analyze customer social media comments and feedback to understand their sentiments	1.16	.59	Very Small Extent
12	manage large volumes of e-mail by automatically categorizing and prioritizing them	1.30	.62	Very Small Extent
Cluster Mean		1.40	.67	Very Lowly Utilized

Table 2 shows a cluster mean score of 1.40 and standard deviation score of .67. This indicates that entrepreneurs in Anambra State to a very small extent leverage natural learning processing (NLP) technologies for successful business management. The item by item analysis shows that entrepreneurs to a small extent leverage items 7 and 8 for successful business management with mean scores of 1.54 to 1.58. The remaining four items are to a very small extent for successful business management with mean scores ranging from 1.16 to 1.41. The standard deviations for all the items ranged from .57 to .84, indicating that the respondents are not wide apart in their ratings.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of entrepreneurs with 6 and above years of working experience and those below 6 years experience on the extent they leverage Machine Learning technologies for successful business management in Anambra State

Table 3: T-test Analysis of Significant Difference in the Mean Ratings of Entrepreneurs on the Extent They Leverage Machine Learning Technologies for Successful Business Management Based on Years of Working Experience

Years of working Experience	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-value	P-value	Decision
6 years and above	189	1.48	.75	304	2.18	1.00	Not Significant
Below 6 years	117	1.35	.69				

Table 3 shows that t-value of 2.18 at 304 degree of freedom (df) with a p-value of 1.00 is greater than the criterion value of 0.05 ($1.00 > 0.05$). Since p-value is greater than the significant value, the null hypothesis is therefore accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of entrepreneurs with 6 and above years of working experience and those below 6 years experience on the extent they leverage Machine Learning technologies for successful business management in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of entrepreneurs on the extent they leverage Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies for successful business management in Anambra State based on years of working experience.

Table 4: T-test Analysis of Significant Difference in the Mean Ratings of Entrepreneurs on the Extent They Leverage Natural Language Processing (NLP) Technologies for Successful Business Management Based on Years of Working Experience

Years of working Experience	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	t-value	P-value	Decision
6 years and above	189	1.53	.75	304	2.34	1.06	Not Significant
Below 6 years	117	1.48	.86				

Table 4 shows that t-value of 2.34 at 304 degree of freedom (df) with a p-value of 1.06 is greater than the criterion value of 0.05 ($1.06 > 0.05$). Since p-value is greater than the significant value, the null hypothesis is therefore accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of entrepreneurs on the extent they leverage Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies for successful business management in Anambra State based on years of working experience.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings of the study revealed that entrepreneurs in Anambra State to a very small extent leverage machine learning technologies for successful business management. This finding could be attributed to lack or inadequate digital skills by these entrepreneurs or lack of awareness of the entrepreneurs on the benefits of leveraging AI for business. In support, Omole and Fasina (2024) revealed that most entrepreneurs are not aware of the benefits of leveraging AI in business. Ebuka et al. (2023) reported that most SMEs in Nigeria are still operating manually; hence, they do not enjoy the massive potential of AI deployment and remain perpetually small in size. This supports the earlier findings of Eze, Chinedu-Eze and Bello (2021) that the main reasons for the low adoption of AI technologies by entrepreneurs include lack of awareness, high costs of AI integration, and limited technical skills among entrepreneurs. Findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of entrepreneurs with 6 and above years of experience and those below 6 years of experience on the extent they leverage machine learning technologies for successful business management in Anambra State. In agreement, Obioha and Umoh (2021) found no significant relationship between the years of work experience of entrepreneurs and their willingness to adopt digital technologies.

Findings of the study revealed that entrepreneurs in Anambra State to a very small extent leverage NLP technologies for successful business management. This finding concurs with the findings of Adegboye and Osunmakinde (2022) that AI awareness was generally low, and most business owners perceived AI technologies as too advanced for their operations. Adegboye and Osunmakinde attributed this to a lack of digital infrastructure and poor understanding of AI's potential benefits. Ibidunni, Abiodun and Adebisi (2020) found that while most firms used some form of digital technology, only 12% had integrated AI tools. Findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of entrepreneurs on the extent they leverage Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies for successful business management in Anambra State based on years of working experience. Supporting this finding, Adeyemi and Olamide (2020) revealed that younger and older entrepreneurs alike adopted digital tools when they perceived a competitive advantage or received training, regardless of their experience.

CONCLUSION

The study was carried out to determine the extent AI technologies are leveraged for successful business management by entrepreneurs in Anambra State. It was found that entrepreneurs to a very small extent leverage machine learning technologies and NLP technologies for successful business management in Anambra State. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concludes that entrepreneurs in Anambra State are not adequately leveraging the impact of AI technologies for enhancing the success of their business management.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher makes the following recommendations;

1. Anambra State Ministry of Commerce and Industry should organize workshops, seminars and training programmes to increase awareness among SMEs on the potential benefits of AI technologies in business management. These awareness programmes should focus on how machine learning and NLP technologies can simplify operations, enhance decision-making, and improve overall business performance.
2. Anambra State government agencies and private organizations should create strategies that provide subsidized access to AI tools and software, making it easier for SMEs to leverage AI technologies without incurring high initial costs. This could be done through partnerships with technology firms or AI service providers.
3. Anambra State government should encourage the development of simplified and affordable AI technologies tailored specifically to the needs of SMEs in the state. This could involve local technology companies or start-ups creating industry-specific AI applications that address the unique challenges faced by entrepreneurs in the region.
4. The Anambra State government should provide financial incentives, such as tax breaks, grants, or low-interest loans, to SMEs that greatly leverage AI technologies. These incentives could help reduce the financial burden on entrepreneurs looking to leverage AI into their business operations, thus encouraging greater adoption.
5. Entrepreneurs in Anambra State should go for more digital skill acquisition trainings to enhance their AI skills. This will help them to leverage AI technologies for successful business management.

REFERENCES

- Adegboye, A. A., & Osunmakinde, I. O. (2022). *Artificial intelligence and entrepreneurship in Nigeria: Challenges and opportunities*. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 12(1), 101-117.
- Adeyemi, A. A., & Olamide, O. R. (2020). *Technology readiness and digital transformation in African enterprises: Experience does not matter*. *African Journal of Business Management*, 14(9), 240-253.
- Adeyemi, S. L. & Olufemi, O. F. (2016). The role of entrepreneurship in economic development: The Nigerian perspective. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 7(14), 128-132.
- Awoyemi, J. O., et al. (2017). *Credit card fraud detection using machine learning techniques*. *Journal of Finance and Data Science*.

- Chaffey, D. (2020). *AI in marketing: 20+ examples of Artificial Intelligence in Marketing* [Online]. Available at Smart Insights.
- Chong, A. Y. L., et al. (2017). Predicting e-commerce adoption in small- and medium-sized enterprises. *Journal of Business Research*, 5(1), 1–11.
- Dan-Awoh, D. (2022, August 29). *Why two million MSMEs collapsed in two years*. Punch Newspapers. <https://punchng.com/why-two-million-msmes-collapsed-in-two-years.com>
- Ebuka, A. A., Emmanuel, D., & Idigo, P. (2023). Artificial Intelligence as a catalyst for the Sustainability of Small and Medium Scale Businesses (SMEs) in Nigeria. *Annals of Management and Organization Research*, 5(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.35912/amor.v5i1.1719>
- Eze, S. C., Chinedu-Eze, V. C., & Bello, A. O. (2021). *Artificial intelligence adoption in SMEs: Evidence from Lagos, Nigeria*. *International Journal of Innovation Science*, 13(4), 541-554.
- Gitman, L. J. (2018). *Principles of Managerial Finance*. Pearson.
- Gupta, R. & Katoch, H. (2023). Role of artificial intelligence in business management. *International Journal for Multidimensional Research Perspectives*, 1(3), 175-185.
- Ibidunni, O. S., Abiodun, A. J., & Adebisi, S. O. (2020). *Adoption of technological innovations in Nigerian manufacturing SMEs: The role of AI and robotics*. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 155, 119938.
- Joel, I. C., Michael, A. & Bolouimbelemoere, K. P. (2023) Impact of digital transformation on Nigeria business growth. *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research and Studies*, 3(3), 18-23.
- Joseph, B. (2023, June 23). *80% of SMEs fails in Nigeria due to economic challenges and regulatory constraints- report*. MSME Africa Online. <https://msmeafricaonline.com/80-of-smes-fails-in-nigeria-due-to-economic-challenges-and-regulatory-constraints-report.com>
- Kaufmann, K. (2023). The essential components of successful business management. <https://kariykaufmann.com/successful-business-management/20involves%20objectives>
- Kings, S. (2018). Financial problems and survival strategies of small scale enterprises in Awka south L.G.A, anambra state. *Afribary*. <https://afribary.com/works/financial-problems-and-survival-strategies-of-small-scale-enterprises-in-awka-south-l-g-a-anambra-state-1147>
- Nwite, S. (2025, March 11). *Nigerian economy in crisis: 7.2 Million MSMEs shut down in 2023 & 2024 – NESG*. Tekedia. <https://www.tekedia.com/nigerian-economy-in-crisis-7-2-million-msmes-shut-down-in-2023-2024-nesg.com>
- Obidile, J. I., Nwankwo, P. N., & Okpara, L. (2022). determination of factors affecting the growth and survival of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Anambra State. *International Journal of Education Humanities and Social Science*, 5(03), 162-171. ² <http://ijehss.com/>
- Obioha, C. E., & Umoh, G. I. (2021). *Determinants of digital technology adoption in Nigerian SMEs: A focus on experience and other factors*. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*, 28(3), 461-478.
- Oduntan, E. B. & Isere, V. O. M. (2022). Digital technologies for business sustainability in Nigeria: An empirical analysis. *African Journal of Management and Business Research*, 5(1), 12-22.
- Omole, O. J. & Fasina, O. O. (2024) Utilization of artificial intelligence-enabled technologies by agripreneurs in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Agricultural Sciences*, 15, 439-448. <https://doi.org/10.4236/as.2024.154026>
- Ranco, L. (2021). 6 major sub-fields of artificial intelligence. <https://rancholabs.medium.com/6-major-sub-fields-of-artificial-intelligence-77f6a5b28109>
- Takyar, A. (2024). AI in business management: Use cases, benefits and technologies. <https://www.leewayhertz.com/ai-in-business-management/>
- Ufoegbunam, C., & Anekwe, R. I. (2024). Entrepreneurial readiness and sustainability of small and medium scale enterprises in Anambra State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5(2), 12-25. <https://journals.unizik.edu.ng/ijbmr/article/view/430.com>
- Wang, H., et al. (2019). *Sales forecasting using machine learning techniques*. *Journal of Business Analytics*, 4(2), 43-55.